

Local Government in Australia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The Country Report on Local Government in Australia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Australia: An Introduction

Carol Mills, Institute for Public Policy and Governance, University of Technology Sydney

From 1992 to 2020, local governments were represented at Australia's chief intergovernmental forum, the Council of Australian Governments (COAG), through the Australian Local Government Association (ALGA).

COAG was established to improve and promote intergovernmental arrangements. It sought to ensure co-operation between all levels of government and increase structural efficiency. It also aimed to find ways to enhance accountability, as service delivery in Australia is often poorly delineated between different levels of government. COAG focused on key policy reforms of national significance, such as the National Competition Policy.

ALGA is the peak body of state local government associations. It advocates on behalf of its members and has historically represented local government at a range of national government committees and forums. ALGA's board is made up of 2 representatives of each state association plus an independent chair. ALGA was a member of COAG, together with the Australian Government, the governments of the six states and two mainland territories.

When created, COAG replaced Premiers' Conferences and, progressively, a large number of Ministerial Councils including the Council on Local Government. Through ALGA, local government had observer status at some of these meetings, but formal membership was normally restricted to state and federal government representatives.

On 29 May 2020, in response to the crisis brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic, the Australian Prime Minister announced the establishment of a National Cabinet to replace COAG. The National Cabinet is now the country's chief inter-governmental decision-making body. It comprises the Premiers and Chief Ministers of the eight states and territories and the Prime Minister. ALGA, and by extension local government, is not a member of this Cabinet. Within this new institutional landscape, the Commonwealth may be more inclined to leave local government issues to the states, and state governments might become more centralist, increasing their control over local governments. This is a particular risk during and post-Covid where state and local government revenue bases have been much reduced and many local governments will likely not be financially viable without increased state support.

In this context, and during a time of major change, ALGA found itself potentially marginalised and expressed concern that the voice of local government would not be heard. While there have been calls for a decision about appropriate governance arrangements remain, the current question is how local government should position itself within this evolving institutional context.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Phillimore J and Fenna A, 'Intergovernmental Councils and Centralization in Australian Federalism' (2017) 27 *Regional and Federal Studies* 597
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